

Development of aptamer-biofunctionalized magnetic nanoparticles for the detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers

Katsipis Georgios, Post-Doctoral Researcher, LND Group, CIRI, AUTH, katsiphs.g1@gmail.com

Tzekaki Eleni, Post-Doctoral Researcher, LND Group, CIRI, AUTH, etzekaki@chem.auth.gr

Makridis Antonios, Post-Doctoral Researcher, anmakrid@physics.auth.gr

Kazeli Konstantina, PhD candidate, kazeli.konstantina@gmail.com

Angelakeris Makis, Professor, agelaker@auth.gr

Pantazaki Anastasia, Professor, LND Group, CIRI, AUTH, natasa@chem.auth.gr

The establishment of novel diagnostic methodologies for the early detection of Alzheimer's disease (AD) is imperative, to prevent the progression of dementia, inability, and institutionalization. ELISA and enzymatic chemiluminescence methodologies that employ antibodies, often lack the necessary sensitivity for detecting AD biomarkers. In addition, antibodies are extremely sensitive to various environmental factors, and their production is expensive and with ethical considerations. Aptamers are stable, cost-effective oligonucleotides that can bind several molecular targets with high sensitivity and specificity. The functionalization of magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) with aptamers is a novel approach for developing ultra-sensitive analytical methodologies. Antibody-functionalized MNPs are already included in sensitive automatic analyzers for the detection of disease-related biomarkers. The binding of aptamers on MNPs increases the stability of the bound biomolecule and offers the potential for stereochemical-determined interactions and magnetism-driven orientation and wash-off. In 2D-BioPAD, we already have functionalized Au-Fe-MNPs with the aptamers targeting amyloid beta (A β) peptides: RNV95 and A β 7-92-1H1, with two different conjugation methodologies: treatment with 1) low-pH citrate buffer, 2) freeze-thaw. Our immediate aim is to optimize the experimental factors for sensitive and specific detection of A β and for succeeding in the detection of other crucial AD biomarkers, like p-tau, GFAP and NfL.

4 key words

Alzheimer Diagnosis

Magnetic Nanoparticles

Aptamers

Biomarkers